

**ADSORPTION EQUILIBRIUM AND KINETICS STUDIES OF
DIVALENT MANGANESE FROM PHOSPHORIC ACID SOLUTION BY
USING CATIONIC EXCHANGE RESIN.**

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Abstract. There are numerous impurities in wet-process phosphoric acid, among which manganese is one of detrimental metallic impurities, and it causes striking negative effects on the industrial phosphoric acid production and downstream commodity. This article investigated the adsorption behavior of manganese from phosphoric acid employing Sinco-430 cationic ion-exchange resin. Resorting FT-IR and XPS characterizations, the adsorption mechanism was proved to be that manganese was combined with sulfonic acid group. Several crucial parameters such as temperature, phosphoric acid content and resin dose were studied to optimize adsorption efficiency. Through optimization, removal percentage and sorption capacity of manganese reached 53.12 wt%, 28.34 mg·g⁻¹, respectively. Pseudo-2nd-order kinetic model simulated kinetics data best and the activation energy was evaluated as 6.34 kJ·mol⁻¹ for the sorption reaction of manganese. In addition, the global adsorption rate was first controlled by film diffusion process and second

determined by pore diffusion process. It was found that the resin could adsorb up to $50.24 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ for manganese. Equilibrium studies showed that Toth adsorption isotherm model fitted best, followed by Temkin and Langmuir adsorption isotherm models. Thermodynamic analysis showed that manganese adsorption was an endothermic process with enhanced randomness and spontaneity.

Keywords: Manganese, Ion exchange, Phosphoric acid, Kinetics, Isotherm, Thermodynamics.

Introduction. Phosphoric acid is a kind of basic chemical feedstock, which is extensively used in numerous industrial categories such as chemical fertilizers, detergents, food additives, electronic, medicine, beverages and so on [1–3]. Currently, phosphoric acid is produced industrially in two main ways, including thermal and wet methods. The thermal method technique is comprised of the combustion oxidation of yellow phosphorus and hydration absorption of phosphorus pentoxide, which although obtain highly purified phosphoric acid, it consumes much more energy than that of wet method [4]. In addition, the wet method is more environmentally friendly than the former. Wet method primarily decomposes phosphate rock with inorganic acid [3], and then separates the insoluble solids from the liquid phase. Therein, sulfuric acid route is used most widely because of its lower cost and simple operation. For another, with the sharp consumption of high-grade phosphate rock, mid-and-low grade phosphate rock will be mined more widely and intensely [5].

In recent years, most proportion of industrial phosphoric acid was manufactured by wet process [6]. However, undesired impurities in the phosphate rock, such as Fe, Mg, Al, Mn and some other solid and organic matters are leached out together with phosphorus unavoidably [1,2], which will cause a battery of striking undesirable influence to the phosphoric acid purification and subsequent phosphorus based merchandise [7]. For instance, excess content of metal will: (1)

reduce the concentration of solubilized phosphors; (2) lead to serious scaling in the pipes and equipment when enrichment [4]; (3) bring about more transportation cost due to the increasing viscosity of phosphoric acid;

(4) result in the generation of sludge in the wet-process phosphoric acid, which may bring about blockage of pipeline; (5) cause the caking of chemical fertilizer, which is harmful to carriage, storage and application of fertilizer, (6) and so on. In addition, it has to mention that various metallic ions may accumulate in soils and permeate into underground and surface water through the intermediary of phosphate fertilizer [1]. The excess uptake of metallic ions by crop would inevitably lead to the increasing metal level of food and animals. As most metal elements, such as manganese, are not biodegradable, and the degradation ability of living organisms are limited, excess metal will gradually gather in the living organisms, which eventually caused various diseases and disorders to human health [8,9]. Therefore, wet-process phosphoric acid necessarily needs purification before subsequent applications.

Various purification methods could be used in the impurity removing of wet-process phosphoric acid, including chemical precipitation [10,11], solvent extraction [12,13], crystallization [14,15] and ion exchange [16–20]. In these ways, ion exchange method has a great many satisfactory advantages, containing environment friendly, simple operation, financial efficiency and higher selectivity, and it has been widely used in the decontamination of wet-process phosphoric acid as well as some other aqueous systems [19,20]. For instance, in Qiu's investigation on the magnesium adsorption from phosphoric acid, the removal percentage was about 87 wt% [16]. Tang et al. investigated aluminum adsorption behavior in phosphoric acid solution system, and the adsorption process of aluminum accorded with pseudo-2nd-order kinetics model [17]. In Leng's study, the holistic reaction rate of adsorption process was determined by pore diffusion [18]

Results and discussion.

1.1.1. XPS characterization

Fig. 2 (a) presented the wide XPS spectrum of the resin before adsorption, and the main element was C, O, N and S. There was just a sort of binding energy (168.46 eV) for S 2p as shown in Fig. 2 (c), which was due to the function group $\text{—SO}_3\text{H}$. Fig. 2 (d) showed that O 1 s had two types of binding energy, around at 531.74 and 533.44 eV, respectively. The reason of this result was that O 1 s located in the

different positions of molecular structure, i.e., there were two different chemical bonds for O 1 s ($\text{S}=\text{O}$, S—O) [34,35]. Furthermore, the peak area of $\text{S}=\text{O}$ was about twice that of S—O .

The resin after manganese adsorption was also characterized by XPS, and its full spectrum was depicted in Fig. 3 (a), which indicated that manganese participated in the adsorption reaction with resin indeed. However, the combination of manganese and sulfonic acid group had altered the chemical environment of S and O. The peaks for S 2p at 169.25 eV and 168.07 eV in Fig. 3 (c) revealed the existence of Mn—SO_3 and $\text{—SO}_3\text{H}$ in the resin, respectively. It was found that there were three different peaks for O 1 s, the binding energy of these peaks were 533.70 (Mn—O—S), 532.64 (S—O) and 531.64 eV ($\text{S}=\text{O}$), respectively. Thereinto, the peak at 533.70 eV proved the exchange of manganese and proton.

Fig. 2. XPS spectra of resin before manganese sorption: (a) wide, (b) C 1 s, (c) S 2p, (d) O 1 s.

1.1.2. Reaction mechanism

The mechanism of the reaction between manganese ion and sulfonic acid group is mostly electrostatic interaction, which could be elucidated by Donnan membrane equilibrium theory [21]. Ion-exchange resins are generally composed of polymer chains, and fixed charged groups attached to the chain skeletons. These fixed charges that are bound to the resin phase are the functional groups of the resin, and the mobile charges possessing a sign of charge that is opposite to the fixed charges, are called the counter-ions. Meanwhile, the mobile charges that have the same sign as the fixed charges are called the co-ions [22].

In the ion-exchange resin, solute-matrix interactions (van der Waals forces), ion-dipole interactions (polarization), and ion-solvent interactions (hydration) are

much weaker than electrostatic interactions between resin and ions, their contribution to ion-exchange behavior were usually not considered [23]. In addition, the electrostatic interactions between fixed charges and mobile charges are long-range interaction, hence the resin phase is usually considered as a homogeneous phase [24].

For the ion-exchange system in this paper, the fixed charges of the resin are sulfonic acid groups. Counter-ions present in the phosphoric acid, including Mn^{2+}

and other counter-ions, can exchange with the H^+ previously in the matrix of the resins. However, co-ions in the phosphoric acid (SO_4^{2-} , H_2PO_4^- , HPO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-}) are excluded from the resin because of the Donnan potential at the resin-solution interface [25]. Because sulfonic acid groups are preferentially bonded to bivalent

Mn^{2+} than the monovalent H^+ , the Mn^{2+} ions are therefore enriched in the resin phase, leading to the purification of the phosphoric acid solution.

Conclusion.

In this paper, we triumphantly conducted a systematic investigation on the adsorption behavior of manganese from phosphoric acid using Sinco-430 cation-exchange resin. The results of FT-IR and XPS proved sorption mechanism to be that manganese was combined with $—SO_3H$. Phosphoric acid content and the mass proportion of resin to solution showed significant impact on the manganese adsorption efficiency, while temperature exerted little positive influence. Kinetics study indicated that manganese sorption process could be better represented by pseudo-2nd-order kinetics model, and the activation energy of adsorption reaction was $6.34 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$. The application result of diffusion models showed that the rate-determining step of manganese sorption process was film and pore diffusion process in succession. Isotherm studies showed that the adsorption behavior of the resin followed Toth isotherm model best, and the experimental value of maximum manganese adsorption capacity was $50.24 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, which was almost the same as the calculated value of Toth isotherm model. Manganese sorption process was an endothermic process with entropy increase and spontaneity. The obtained conclusions above indicated that Sinco-430 could be considered as a satisfactory cation exchange resin for the removal of manganese from phosphoric acid.

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